

Practice Guide on the establishment and application of impedance-based measurement procedures to estimate the residual capacity of second-use battery cells

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Scope

The EMPIR project LiBforSecUse aimed to develop empirical measurement models to estimate the residual capacity of second-use Li-ion battery cells with impedance-based measurement and evaluation methods. This practice guide illustrates a methodology that can be used to establish and apply such methods using commercial 18650 cells with graphite/NMC cell chemistry as an example.

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2. Background

In the LiBforSecUse project, regression models were developed to estimate the State-of-Health (SOH) of 18650 lithium-ion batteries based on impedance data (see Deliverable D5 for details). To create these SOH estimation models, life cycle tests (LCTs) were performed with these batteries. This involved the cycling of cells under defined conditions. At intervals of about 50-100 cycles, the SOH of the cells was determined and impedance spectra were measured. The measured spectra were analyzed using three different methods:

- Direct impedance method
- Equivalent circuit (EC) fitting method
- Distribution of Relaxation Times (DRT) method

The impedance parameters derived from the spectra with these methods were subsequently examined for their correlation with the SOH. For this purpose, Pearson and Spearman correlation coefficients were calculated and those parameters with the highest coefficients were selected as predictors for the SOH estimation model. A 4-fold cross-validation approach was used to train and subsequently validate regression models for the three different methods. The results are shown in Figure 1. From the totality of data generated in the LCTs, only those measured at State-of-Charge (SOC) 100% and in the SOH range between 70% and 95% were selected for modeling. The first criterion is used to simplify the adjustment of a defined SOC. This is necessary because the impedance of lithium-ion batteries is strongly dependent on the SOC. The SOH range was selected because it is practical with regard to batteries for secondary use.

Figure 1: Results of the 4-fold cross-validation of the SOH estimation models for the three different evaluation methods: (a) direct impedance evaluation, (b) evaluation of spectra by equivalent circuit fitting, and (c) evaluation of the EIS by DRT. The four different colors represent one of the four runs of the cross validation

In the plots, the SOH estimated with the corresponding model are plotted against the measured SOH. The four different colors of the plot represent one of the four iterations of the cross-validation - consequently, the SOH estimates of all used measurement points of the LCTs are shown in the plots. The comparison of the validation results of the three different methods shows that the predictive strengths do not differ significantly from each other. As an indicator of the quality of the SOH estimates, the RMS error from each estimate was calculated, and the mean values of the four runs of cross-validation are given for each method. They range from 0.8% SOH units for the direct impedance method to 1.2% for the EC method. All models are therefore well suited to estimate the SOH of a cell. It was therefore decided not to determine which model and thus which evaluation method is the most suitable. Instead, it is shown below how the three methods can be used to estimate the SOH of an unknown battery on the basis of an impedance measurement.

For each of the three methods, different programs were developed to process the EIS data and perform the SOH estimation. These programs will be available soon in the LiBforSecUse repository on Zenodo. In the following descriptions, it is noted if a program was developed for a particular data processing step that will be available there.

3. EIS Measurement

In order to accurately estimate the SOH on the basis of an impedance spectrum using the SOH estimation models, it is first necessary to perform an impedance measurement that is as precise as possible. For this purpose, testing conditions were defined that allow such a measurement. Since the impedance of batteries depends in a pronounced way on the SOC, it is necessary to bring the cell under investigation to a defined SOC before the measurement of the EIS. The setting of SOC = 100 % is the clearest compared to all other SOCs: the cell to be tested is simply charged with a defined current (here 1.25 A) up to its end of charge voltage (here 4.15 V). In this way, it is not necessary to set the SOC by Coulomb counting, which would implicitly require knowledge of the SOH. The regression models were therefore trained with impedance data measured at SOC = 100 %. Consequently, the impedance spectrum used to determine the SOH of an unknown cell must also be measured at this SOC. After SOC = 100 % has been set as described above, an impedance spectrum can be measured after a waiting time for relaxation of the cell of 15 minutes. The following parameters must be set for this purpose:

- Upper frequency limit: $f_{\max} = 10^4$ Hz
- Lower frequency limit: $f_{\min} = 10^{-2}$ Hz
- Measuring point density: 10 Points per decade
- Measuring mode: GEIS
- Amplitude: 0.5 A

When parameterizing the spectrum, care should also be taken to ensure that the frequencies specified in section 3.1 are measured. In addition, the frequency points should be distributed as logarithmically as possible, since this is a prerequisite for the calculation of the DRTs. All previously described measurements (i.e. SOC adjustment and EIS measurement) must be performed at 23 °C. Based on an impedance spectrum recorded in compliance with these measurement parameters, the SOH of the cell under consideration can be estimated using the three different models.

A more detailed Guide on low-impedance measurements and LCT test conditions can be found at the LiBforSecUse Repository community at Zenodo.org.

4. Application of the different models for SOH estimation.

The following sections describe in detail how the models created for the three methods mentioned above can be used to estimate the SOH of the corresponding cell from the previously measured impedance spectrum.

Direct impedance-based method

In this method, the aging parameters required for SOH estimation are derived directly from the impedance spectrum. These are the real parts (Z') and imaginary parts (Z'') of the impedance at the following frequencies:

1. Z' at 0.03 Hz
2. Z' at 0.01 Hz
3. Z'' 0.2 Hz
4. Z'' 0.5 Hz

If only the direct impedance method is to be used for SOH estimation, a direct measurement of the four mentioned frequencies can also be performed instead of recording an entire impedance spectrum. If a complete spectrum is recorded, care should be taken to ensure that the required measurement points are actually measured. If this is not possible due to restrictions of the impedance spectrometer used, the corresponding frequencies can be determined by interpolation. A program to perform the interpolation will be available in the LiBforSecUse Repository. After the four aging parameters have been determined, they can be fed into the direct impedance regression model which will be available in the LiBforSecUse Repository. The SOH of the cell is calculated.

EC-based method

When estimating the SOH with the EC-based method, two different programs are used successively: in the first one, the equivalent circuit fitting is performed. The Matlab based program optimized for the fitting of spectra of 18650 type cells will be available in the LiBforSecUse Repository and can be used for this purpose. Alternatively, any other equivalent circuit fitting program (e.g. ZView) can be used. After the impedance parameters have been determined from the spectrum by fitting, they are fed into the SOH estimation model which will be available in the LiBforSecUse Repository.

For the equivalent circuit fitting, the equivalent circuit shown in Figure 2 is used. A total of twelve different parameters are derived from its nine elements.

Figure 2: equivalent circuit for the fitting of impedance spectra

To perform the equivalent circuit fitting, the initial values listed in Table 1 are used for the various coefficients. These are set as defaults in the above mentioned program. Furthermore, upper and lower limits for the respective coefficient are defined therein. When using other programs for equivalent circuit fitting, the initial values should be taken from the table and, if possible, also the limit values.

Table 1: initial values and boundary conditions for the equivalent circuit fitting

Coefficient	Unit	Lower bound	Upper bound	Initial value
R_s	Ω	0	∞	1
L_s	H	0	∞	1
R_p	Ω	0	∞	1
L_p	H	0	∞	1
$R_{ct,1}$	Ω	0	∞	1
$\omega_{dl,1}$	rad s^{-1}	ω_{\min}	ω_{\max}	$10^{2.8}$
$\alpha_{dl,1}$	1	0.5	1	1
$R_{ct,2}$	Ω	0	0	1
$\omega_{dl,2}$	rad s^{-1}	ω_{\min}	ω_{\max}	$10^{0.4}$
$\alpha_{dl,2}$	1	0.5	1	1
Q_{diff}	C	0	∞	1
α_{diff}	1	0.5	1	1

The developed program offers a batch mode for the evaluation of multiple spectra. After the fitting, the parameters $R_{ct,2}$, $C_{dl,2}$, $\alpha_{dl,2}$, Q_{diff} and α_{diff} are transferred into the EC-based regression model. The SOH calculation is then performed.

DRT-based model

For the evaluation of impedance spectra by DRT, it must first be checked if frequencies in the measured spectrum are logarithmically distributed and if the distances are constant over the entire frequency range. If this is not the case, an interpolation of the frequency points must be performed. The required program will be available in the LiBforSecUse Repository.

Before the DRT can be calculated from the measured impedance data a preprocessing of the spectrum must be performed. Therein the inductive and diffusive parts of the spectrum are fitted and subsequently subtracted from the entire spectrum. This step is essential for an error-free DRT calculation since the two mentioned parts of the spectrum cannot be sensibly captured by the DRT deconvolution. It is also not possible to simply remove the data points of the corresponding parts from the spectrum, since they overlap with relevant parts of the spectrum and the erroneous influence would thus not be eliminated. The preprocessing is divided into the following three steps:

- 1) First of the ranges over which the inductive or diffusive part of the spectrum is to be fitted are determinate. For the inductive part of the spectrum, the first four frequency points of the spectrum are selected. To determine a suitable range for fitting the diffusive part of the spectrum, the local maximum, which marks the transition between the polarization range and the diffusion range in the spectrum, is determined. Relative to this point, the ten higher and the six lower frequency points are selected. The two selected ranges are fitted in the next step. For the identification of the two mentioned ranges a Matlab tool will be available in the LiBforSecUse Repository. This tool outputs the two described ranges as txt file. These can be read in the following into an equivalent circuit fitting program.
- 2) The two files of the previously generated partial spectra are read into a program for equivalent circuit fitting. In the project ZView (Scribner Associates Inc., USA) was used for this purpose. In it, the inductive part of the spectrum is fitted with the equivalent circuit shown in Figure 2 a, the diffusive part with the one shown in Figure 2b.

Figure 3: equivalent circuits for the partial fitting of (a) inductive part and (b) diffusive part of the spectrum

Suitable initial values for fitting with the two equivalent circuits are given in Table 2. Batch mode can be used to perform the fitting. In this case, previous fits should not be used as new initial values.

Table 2: initial values for the equivalent circuit fitting with the circuits given in Figure 3

Circuit (a)		Circuit (b)	
Coefficient	Initial value	Coefficient	Initial value
R_s	0.015	R_s	0.02
L_s	10^{-8}	R_{ct}	0.02
		C_{ct}	10
		W_R	0.05
		W_T	10
		W_P	0.5 (fixed)

In the final step, the impedance of the corresponding element (in the inductive part the inductance L and in the diffusive part the Warburg impedance W_s) is calculated from the impedance parameters determined in the fitting for all frequency points of the measured spectrum. These impedance values are then subtracted from the measured spectrum for each frequency point. When using ZView, this process can be performed in the program. However, there is no batch mode available, making the procedure very time-consuming when processing multiple spectra. Alternatively a Matlab tool can be used which will be available in the LiBforSecUse Repository. The results of the batch fitting of the partial spectra can be imported into that program from ZView-files. The underlying original spectra are then loaded and the subtraction is performed. The DRTs can now be calculated from the resulting preprocessed spectra.

The calculation of the DRT is performed in a modified version of the program DRTtools. In it, the preprocessed spectra are imported and the DRTs are output for the different data sets (real part, imaginary part and combined data set) of the spectrum and for different regularization parameters. In addition, the output of the parameters derived from the DRTs (time constants, resistances, capacitances, peak resolution, etc.) is done in a separate file. The two predictors (τ_s and R_s) for the SOH estimation can also be taken from this file. It should be noted that the combined data set of real and imaginary parts must be selected as the basis for the SOH estimation, as well as a regularization parameter of 10^{-5} . These two parameters are imported into the program of the DRT-based regression model which calculates the SOH.

5. Conclusions

Impedance spectra can be evaluated in three different ways to generate aging parameters for a corresponding SOH estimation models. The predictive strength of the three models differs only slightly from each other. In terms of usability, the direct impedance-based model is the most suitable, since the required predictors for the regression model can be taken directly from the raw data of the impedance spectra. The EC-based model has a similarly good practicability. Here, the predictors for the regression model can be determined directly with the delivered program and then transferred to the regression model. In the future, it is planned to combine the two programs so that the SOH can be calculated directly from a spectrum. The DRT-based model requires the most sub-steps so far. In the future, it is planned to develop solutions that avoid the use of external programs and combine as many substeps as possible in one program. This concerns above all the preprocessing of the spectra. This is to be integrated into an extended version of DRTtools, so that the DRT can be calculated directly from a measured spectrum. A link with the regression model as intended for the EC-based method is also possible.